

Wf4Ever: Advanced Workflow Preservation Technologies for Enhanced Science

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Best Practices for Archival Processing of Research Objects

Document for the Wf4Ever Knowledge Hub (a librarian view)

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Executive Summary

A Research Object is a multidimensional digital object which comprises elements that describe the way research findings are produced since the formulation of a hypothesis, the design and execution of the experiments, the analysis of results and the conclusion makings. The concept of Research Object is largely motivated by the needs to address the actual challenges associated with knowledge communication.

These new digital objects have been defined in the context of the European Wf4Ever project (<http://www.wf4ever-project.org/>), focused on the provision of technological support for their preservation and efficient retrieval and reuse.

Following the approach developed by the GeoMAPP's [1] previous awarded work¹ this document presents a suggested workflow for archival processing of Research Objects. These best practices are for librarians who want to support research preservation with novel techniques and revolutionize their conventional role as document stewards – they can start to preserve not only research data, but also the methods and the documentation of the role of these data and methods in leading to the outcomes reported in digital publications. In particular, these best practices intend to be useful for digital libraries managers and designers of any scientific workflow infrastructure.

The first part of the document offers a brief introduction to OAIS, as it provides the general framework and basis for an archival processing workflow. In the second part, high level storage architecture is presented that supports the multi-phase archival processing workflow. The third part of the document is the major focus, and offers an RO processing workflow based on the OAIS model to receive submissions, archive, and make accessible Research Objects from archival repositories. Some key questions for an RO-infrastructure with regard to each process are presented.

The digital library framework proposed extends the traditional one, mostly used for documents and non-executable digital content, with the notion of dynamic digital objects linked with semantic relations, supporting the evolution of these objects, and with specialized preservation features, such as monitoring of workflow decay or other issues compromising the reproducibility of experiments.

This document provides information at varying levels of detail. We suggest several “trails” through it depending on your interest:

- If you are already familiar with the notion of ROs, go directly to section 2.
- If you are interested in the technology needed to storage ROs, read section 3.
- If you are responsible for a library, read mainly sections 1 and 4.

¹ It was the 2012 recipient of the Preservation Publication Award given by the Society of American Archivists.

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1. Introduction

Scholarly articles are still the main means, to date, to communicate research findings. However, they are insufficient to communicate all the scientific knowledge behind those findings. New digital artefacts are emerging in data-intensive science. For example, scientific workflows are executable descriptions of scientific procedures that define the sequence of computational steps in an automated data analysis, supporting reproducible research and the sharing and replication of best-practice and know-how through reuse. Workflows are specified at design time and interpreted through their execution in a variety of situations, environments, and domains. Hence it is essential to preserve both their static and dynamic parts.

To achieve this, the Wf4Ever team has proposed the use of complex, multidimensional digital objects (Research Objects, hereafter, mainly referred to as ROs) that aggregate a number of resources used and/or produced in scientific investigations, including workflow models, provenance of their executions, and links to the relevant associated resources, along with the provision of technological support for their preservation and efficient retrieval and reuse.

1.1 Resources and Information Objects

A Resource is an abstract definition which covers any entity that can be identified, named or addressed in the Web. According to the Digital Reference Model [2, p.38], this novel understanding fits very well with the meaning assumed by the same term in the Digital Library universe. Instances of the concept of Resource in the Digital Library universe are Information Objects.

Within the context of the OAIS (Open Archival Information System) Reference Model², ISO 14721-2012 standard [3], an Information Object is composed of a Data Object that is either physical or digital, and the Representation Information that allows for the full interpretation of the data into meaningful information.

All the different types of resources [2, p.38] share many characteristics and ways in which they can be related to other resources. Each resource is:

- Identified by a “resource identifier”.
- Arranged or laid out according to a “resource format”.
- Characterised by various “quality parameters”, each capturing how the resource performs with respect to some attribute.
- Regulated by “policies” governing every aspect of its lifetime.
- Expressed by an “information object”.
- Described by or commented on by an “information object”, especially by those dedicated to record “metadata”, “annotations”, “context” or “provenance”.

² A more detailed explanation about OAIS Reference Model is available at section 1.5

1.2 Research Objects as aggregations of resources³

Research Objects comprise elements that describe the way research findings are produced since the formulation of a hypothesis, the design and execution of the experiments, the analysis of results and the conclusion makings. These elements include:

- Data used or results produced in an experiment study.
- Methods employed to produce and analyse that data.
- Provenance and setting information about the experiments.
- People involved in the investigation.
- Annotations about these resources, which are essential to the understanding and interpretation of the scientific outcomes captured by a research object.

In conclusion, an RO is essentially an aggregation of these resources. Figure 1 provides an overview of the RO Model, which includes the following constructs:

- **ResearchObject**: Represents an aggregation of resources. It acts as an entry point to the research object.
- **Resource**: Represents a resource that can be aggregated within a research object. A resource can be a workflow, web service, document, data item, data set, workflow run, software or a research object. Typically, a Research Object aggregates multiple Resources.
- **Annotation**: Used for describing research objects, their aggregated resources, as well as the relationship between resources. Three kinds of elements are used to specify annotations:
 - Annotation: Represents the annotation itself.
 - Target: Used to specify the resource or research object subject to annotation.
 - Body: Comprises a description of the target in the form of a set of RDF statements, which can be specifying the date of creation of the target, or its relationship with other resources or research objects.

³ General information on Research Objects in <http://www.researchobject.org/>

Figure 1. Basic aggregation structure of an RO.

A special kind of ROs is workflow-centric ROs, which refer to research objects that aggregate workflows, or more specifically workflow templates:

- A workflow template is a network in which the nodes are processes and the edges represent data links that connect the output of a given process to the input of another process, specifying that the artefacts produced by the former are used to feed the latter.
- A process is used to describe a class of actions that when enacted give rise to process runs. Processes specify the software component (e.g., web service) responsible for undertaking those actions.

A Research Object can be identified by a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), like the Digital Object Identifier (DOI). In this way, an RO can be shared and cited in scholarly articles or any form of online communications, providing an essential collection of contextual information for re-users, reviewers or collaborators to understand, reuse, validate and reproduce research findings.

1.3 A model for Research Objects

Research Objects allow for the aggregation of resources along with annotations on those resources concerning their provenance, use, characteristics, etc. The unit that collects these resources is the RO, and it is described in an RDF-based manifest file (`.ro/manifest.json`) according to the Wf4Ever OWL ontologies.

Aggregation is supported through the use of the OAI-ORE vocabulary⁴ and annotation is supported through the use of the Annotation Ontology⁵ (AO).

Re-use of these existing vocabularies will facilitate third party tools in understanding and processing Research Objects described using the RO Model [6].

Specifically, the RO extends ORE to define three new concepts: i) **ro:ResearchObject** is a sub-class of **ore:Aggregation** which represents an aggregation of resources; ii) **ro:Resource** is a sub-class of

⁴ <http://www.openarchives.org/ore/terms/>

⁵ <http://purl.org/ao>

ore:AggregatedResource representing a resource that is aggregated within an RO; iii) **ro:Manifest** is a sub-class of **ore:ResourceMap**, representing a resource that is used to describe the RO.

Regarding the Annotation Ontology, this provides a common model for annotating resources. Several types of annotations are supported by the Annotation Ontology, e.g., comments, textual annotations (classic tags) and semantic annotations, which relate elements of the ROs to concepts from underlying domain ontologies. The RO model uses the following Annotation Ontology terms: i) **ao:Annotation**, which acts as a handle for the annotation; ii) **ao:annotatesResource**, which represents the resource(s)/RO(s) subjects to annotation; iii) **ao:body**, which describes the target of the annotation. The body of the annotation takes the form of a set of RDF statements. Note that it is planned for later revisions of the RO model to use the successor of AO, the W3C Community Open Annotation Data Model (OA) [7].

The Research Object Model (Figure 2) provides a number of basic ontologies that are used within this aggregation/annotation framework to describe specifics of the Workflow-centric Research Objects. These are:

- The **ro**⁶ **ontology**: Provides basic structure for the description of aggregated resources and the annotations that are made on those resources.
- The **roevo ontology**: Enables the representation of the different stages of the Research Objects life-cycle, their dependencies, as well as the corresponding versions of Research Objects and their aggregated resources, with the associated changes in these resources.
- The **wfdesc**⁷ **ontology**: A vocabulary for the description of workflows. It is targeted at providing an abstraction that can be mapped to different particular workflow systems.
- The **wfprov**⁸ **ontology**: A vocabulary for the description of provenance information about actual executions of workflows.

⁶ <http://purl.org/wf4ever/ro>

⁷ <http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc>

⁸ <http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfprov>. This provides an abstraction that can be mapped to different provenance vocabularies, for example PROV-O5 as developed by the W3C Provenance Working Group.

Figure 2. Research Object Model.

The RO ontologies contain extension points that allow third parties to customise them in order to define specific kinds of research objects or to describe more detailed information that is specific to their tools and application scenarios⁹.

An example of a basic RO is shown below: The "Hello World" example RO aggregates a collection of resources, including the simple Hello World workflow template, its intermediate and final data results resulting from the run of this workflow, as well as annotations to this RO and its components.

```
<> a ro:ResearchObject, ore:Aggregation ;
    ore:aggregates <helloworld.t2flow> ;
    ore:aggregates <artifact/hello> ;
    ore:aggregates :ann1 ;
    dct:created "2011-12-02T15:01:10Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dct:creator [ a foaf:Person; foaf:name "Stian Soiland-Reyes" ] .

<helloworld.t2flow>    rdf:type ro:Resource .
<artifact/hello>      rdf:type ro:Resource .
```

The structure of the workflow in ROs is detailed using the **wfdesc** vocabulary, and is defined as a graph in which the nodes refers to steps in the workflow, called **wfdesc:Process**, and the edges representing data flow dependencies, **wfdesc:DataLink**, which is a link between the output and input parameters (**wfdesc:Parameter**) of the processes that compose the workflow.

As well as the description of the workflow, workflow centric ROs support the specification of the workflow runs, **wfprov:WorkflowRun**, that are obtained as a result of enacting workflows. A workflow run is specified using the **wfprov** ontology, which captures information about the input used to feed the workflow execution, the output results of the workflow run, as well as the constituent process runs, **wfprov:ProcessRun**, of the workflow run, which are obtained by invoking the workflow processes, and the input and outputs of those process runs.

The next one is an example of a basic Workflow Research Object:

```
<> a ro:WorkflowResearchObject ;
    ore:aggregates <helloworld.t2flow> ;
    ore:aggregates <artifact/hello> ;
    ore:aggregates :ann1 ;
    dct:created "2011-12-02T15:01:10Z"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dct:creator [ a foaf:Person; foaf:name "Stian Soiland-Reyes" ] .

<helloworld.t2flow>    rdf:type wfdesc:Workflow .
```

⁹ Details about the RO model and its implementations as ontologies can be found in [the Wf4Ever project website](#).

```
<artifact/hello>      rdf:type      wfprov:Artifact .
```

1.4 The life cycle of an RO

A generalized version of the life cycle of an RO from its creation to its final destination in the archival repository for long-term preservation is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The life cycle of an RO.

A Research Object can be in one of the following stages:

- **LiveRO:** Represents a work in progress. They are thus mutable as the content or state of their resources may change. That is:
 - They are private to the researcher or they are shared with others collaborators via mail, in a common space/server, or with the help of collaborative tools like Dropbox, SVN, Github, etc.
 - They may be versioned with tools like Github or SVN (e.g., as it happens with educational resources as described in <http://mashe.hawksey.info/2012/03/do-you-git-it-open-educational-resourcespractices-meets-software-version-control/>)
 - They are potentially under the control of multiple owners and may fall under mixed stewardship, raising issues of security and access control; however, these issues are addressed by the collaborative and versioning tools used for maintaining LiveROs.

- When a LiveRO at a certain point in time during its evolution needs to be disseminated or preserved, a SnapshotRO or ArchivedRO needs to be made (see below).
- **SnapshotRO:** Is intended as a record of past activity, ready to be disseminated as a whole. They are immutable, and reflect the state of the Live RO at a certain time.
 - Successive snapshots may be related to each other via versioning relations.
 - They can be stored in a Digital Library (and potentially Journal DL infrastructure).
 - They can be shared among a group of selected users, for instance with the research group for internal review or with external referees for external review, but they are not publicly available by default.
 - They must be referenceable.
- **ArchivedRO:** Represents the final stage of a Research Object where it has either reached a version that the author prescribes to be stable and meaningful and is appropriate for publication and long term preservation. They are therefore immutable, with no further changes or versions allowed, or have been deprecated.
 - They are usually stored in a Digital Library (or Journal DL infrastructure).
 - Typically they are publicly available but they may also be restricted to a certain group of people.
 - Desirably curated.
 - They must be citable.
 - They must be preserved.
- **PublicationRO:** Publication here represents the process by which a value of trust is added to a scientific investigation represented by an RO. The process conforms to common practices within a research community, which is typically more than simply making the RO publicly accessible. This usually means some form of peer review.

Each RO may have a label/Tag, identifying a more detailed information of its state, e.g., 'internally-reviewed', 'in progress of internal revision', 'in progress of modifications', 'peer-reviewed', 'ready-to-publish', etc.

1.5 Aim of these Best Practices

The Wf4Ever's team has been working on the design and implementation of software systems for Workflow-centric Research Objects. As one of the results of Wf4Ever's work, this document presents a suggested processing workflow for archival processing of Research Objects.

According to the EC Research Data e-Infrastructures Framework [4], the stewardship of research data remains uncertain: beyond the scientist(s) or laboratories that produce data, no specific group or profession (such as librarians for publications) is in charge of the preservation and organization of data. This makes

data very vulnerable whenever institutional shifts occur (without mentioning broader concerns such as political or economic instability).

Within this context, **these best practices are for librarians who want to support research preservation with novel techniques and revolutionize their conventional role as document stewards** – they can start to preserve not only research data, but also the methods and the documentation of the role of these data and methods in leading to the outcomes reported in digital publications. In particular, these best practices intend to be useful for digital libraries managers - mainly, DL designers [2] - of any scientific workflow infrastructure.

The first part of the document offers a brief introduction to OAIS, as it provides the general framework and basis for an archival processing workflow. In the second part, high level storage architecture is presented that supports the multi-phase archival processing workflow. The third part of the document is the major focus, and offers an RO processing workflow based on the OAIS model.

2. The Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Model

OAIS (Open Archival Information System), ISO 14721-2012 standard, is a reference model for digital preservation developed originally by the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) [3]. OAIS describes "open archival information systems" which are concerned with preserving information for the benefit of a designated community¹⁰. The reference model defines the basic functional components of a system dedicated to the long-term preservation of digital information, identifies and describes the entities which constitute the OAIS environment where the archive operates, details the key internal and external system interfaces which allow the interaction with these entities, and characterizes the information objects managed by the system. The reference model also enumerates a set of minimum requirements an archival system is expected to meet.

2.1 OAIS Functional Model

The OAIS functional model comprises six functional entities and related interfaces, as depicted in Figure 4. These main elements represent the high-level services that fulfil the OAIS role of preserving information and making it available to a designated community. Hence, an archive has to implement each of these services to be compliant with OAIS. According to OAIS, the information objects or information packages, managed by these entities comprise content information (the target information to be preserved) and preservation description information (metadata necessary to identify and understand the environment in which the content was created). Information packages are categorized into Submission Information Package (SIP), Archival Information Package (AIP) and Dissemination Information Package (DIP). SIP is the package sent to an OAIS by a Producer¹¹, which is transformed into one or more AIP for preservation. When requested by a Consumer, OAIS provides all or part of the AIP in the form of a DIP.

A short description of the role of each of these entities is provided below.

¹⁰ A designated community is an identified group of potential Consumers who should be able to understand a particular set of information. The Designated Community may be composed of multiple user communities. A Designated Community is defined by the Archive and this definition may change over time [3].

¹¹ According to the Producer-Archive Interface Specification (PAIS) [5], a SIP can simply be a coherent group of Data Objects which is transferred in the same package. A SIP may also contain a pointer to the Data Objects location in case the Data Objects are not physically transferred in the SIP. For example, a URL or FTP site may be referenced in the SIP.

Figure 4. OAIS Functional Entities¹²

- **Ingest:** Provides the services and functions to accept SIPs from Producers and prepare the contents for storage and management within the archive. Ingest functions include receiving SIPs, performing quality assurance on SIPs, generating an Archival Information Package (AIP) which complies with the Archive's data formatting and documentation standards, extracting Descriptive Information from the AIPs for inclusion in the Archive database, and coordinating updates to Archival Storage and Data Management.
- **Archival Storage:** Provides the services and functions for the storage, maintenance and retrieval of AIPs. Archival Storage functions include receiving AIPs from Ingest and adding them to permanent storage, managing the storage hierarchy, refreshing the media on which Archive holdings are stored, performing routine and special error checking, providing disaster recovery capabilities, and providing AIPs to Access to fulfil orders.
- **Data Management:** Provides the services and functions for populating, maintaining, and accessing both Descriptive Information which identifies and documents Archive holdings and administrative data used to manage the Archive. Data Management functions include administering the Archive database functions (maintaining schema and view definitions, and referential integrity), performing database updates (loading new descriptive information or Archive administrative data), performing queries on the data management data to generate query responses, and producing reports from these query responses.
- **Administration:** Provides the services and functions for the overall operation of the Archive system. Administration functions include soliciting and negotiating submission agreements with Producers, auditing submissions to ensure that they meet Archive standards, and maintaining configuration management of system hardware and software. It also provides system engineering functions to monitor and improve Archive operations, and to inventory, report on,

¹² Copy taken from <http://wiki.datadryad.org/wg/dryad/images/5/53/Oais-model.png>

and migrate/update the contents of the Archive. It is also responsible for establishing and maintaining Archive standards and policies, providing customer support, and activating stored requests.

- **Preservation Planning:** Provides the services and functions for monitoring the environment of the OAIS, providing recommendations and preservation plans to ensure that the information stored in the OAIS remains accessible to, and understandable by, the Designated Community over the Long Term, even if the original computing environment becomes obsolete. Preservation Planning functions include evaluating the contents of the Archive and periodically recommending archival information updates, recommending the migration of current Archive holdings, developing recommendations for Archive standards and policies, providing periodic risk analysis reports, and monitoring changes in the technology environment and in the Designated Community's service requirements and Knowledge Base. Preservation Planning also designs Information Package templates and provides design assistance and review to specialize these templates into SIPs and AIPs for specific submissions. Preservation Planning also develops detailed Migration plans, software prototypes and test plans to enable implementation of Administration migration goals.
- **Access:** Provides the services and functions that support Consumers in determining the existence, description location and availability of information stored in the OAIS, and allowing Consumers to request and receive information products. Access functions include communicating with Consumers to receive requests, applying controls to limit access to specially protected information, coordinating the execution of requests to successful completion, generating responses (Dissemination Information Packages, query responses, reports) and delivering the responses to Consumers.

2.2 Research Objects as Information Packages in the OAIS Reference Model

The concept of Information Package in OAIS can be roughly mapped to a Research Object [Figure 5]. Research Objects, similar to Information Packages, are conceptual containers (aggregations) of Resources (Content Information) and annotations about them (metadata).

The packages submitted to the RO infrastructure (SIP) can be basically individual resources (e.g., workflows, datasets) or simple aggregation of resources. Within the RO infrastructure, these resources are transformed into Research Objects, generating metadata during the transformation regarding the provenance, context, semantic relations, etc.

Similarly, one workflow submitted to the infrastructure may generate a Research Object, which will include the original workflow, plus a workflow bundle (a new workflow format), metadata extracted from the workflow regarding its structure (e.g., inputs, outputs), and other metadata generated.

When they are considered to be immutable, ROs are sent to the preservation infrastructure (AIPs). In response to a request, the infrastructure can return (DIP) the whole Research Object, in different

representations (e.g., as a ZIP archive, HTML page, metadata), or it can provide individual resources within the Research Object (e.g., workflows, datasets).

Figure 5. Types of RO components in each type of OAIS Information Packages.

3. Storage architecture for Research Objects

The repository should establish three different storage repositories (or logical repositories) to support the preservation and access to preserved ROs as depicted in Figure 6. Optionally, an external repository may be used to support the frequently evolving research objects. The repositories may be housed in a single or multiple physical repositories, and use the same or differing technologies (e.g. a repository may use a digital preservation solution for the Preservation Repository and specialized digital library solution for the Access Repository). Additionally, as the Preservation Repository does not have the same interactive use requirements as the access and live repositories, it could be implemented with slower (or offline) storage alternatives.

Figure 6. Conceptual Archival System Storage Architecture.

The preserved objects in the repositories can be associated to stages of research objects during their lifetime. Live Repository stores research objects that are being prepared for archival. Unlike traditional repositories, the preparation **process is continuous and can take a long time**, reflecting the development of a digital experiment. The Live Repository offers read and write access and should provide high responsiveness. The Live Repository should accept resources in a variety of formats, facilitating the process of transforming loosely coupled resources into research objects. Additionally, external services may be used for the transformation of specific types of objects into research objects (e.g. a workflow transformation service). While maintaining a research object in the Live Repository, users may optionally use in parallel other external repositories, such as Git or Dropbox.

When an immutable copy of a research object is created, i.e., a snapshot or archived, it is stored in both Access and Preservation Repositories. The Access Repository provides read-only access to the research

objects but provides read-write access to user generated annotations that talk about the preserved objects (comments, ranks, etc). The preserved objects in the Preservation Repository act as secure copies of the objects that are accessed by the users via the Access Repository.

Ideally, each of these repositories will be located on a physically separate machine because of security and performance reasons. Moreover, it would be desirable for the Preservation Repository to be hosted in secure and reliable infrastructure, such as a cloud storage infrastructure, in order to ensure the long-term preservation of digital objects even in the event of a physical failure. However, if you do not have technical infrastructure to support three physical repository systems, the Wf4Ever team suggests that the Live and Access Repositories may be deployed on one physical machine, or even implemented as one software system, while the Preservation Repository may be deployed as a different system, if possible in another machine. Regardless of the physical location, access control policies should be established on the repositories to restrict access based on an individual's role within the archival process and the type of object. For example, you may grant read/write access to producers and contributors for objects in the Live Repository, while restricting read/write access only to the archival processors and/or publishers for objects in the Access/Preservation Repositories.

3.1 Live Repository

Resources, individual or simple aggregations (Submission Information Package) are submitted / ingested into the Live Repository, which is the only repository that allows write access from research object creators and contributors. The Live Repository is a working area for the producers and collaborators where the content is constantly evolving. This repository should enable the transformation of resources (SIP) into research objects. Digital objects in the Live Repository are stored using the Research Object Model, which differentiates it from other external repositories which may store the same data as individual resources or simple aggregations of resources, depending on the technology used.

3.2 Preservation Repository

The Preservation Repository holds the Preservation Master and archival metadata for the preserved research objects (Archival Information Package). In order to ensure on-going data authenticity and reliability, security on the Preservation Repository should be tightly controlled. Ideally access (both read and write) to this repository will be limited to archival processors or personnel with archival management responsibility. Changes to the preserved objects, i.e., snapshots/archived ROs, should be disallowed. This repository should also set up the mechanisms to protect against any unexpected loss of data, e.g., due to hardware failure. Hence it may create security copies of preserved objects or ideally multiple copies by using a cloud storage infrastructure. There should be minimal access to the Preservation Master, as access often introduces the opportunity to damage the objects. The preservation system needs some sort of service or mechanism to establish and track the fixity, and verify the integrity of the preserved objects. Ideally, the Preservation Repository will also include services to perform periodic integrity checks, and automatically restore or recover preserved objects in the event a corrupted state. Moreover, since this repository has the secure copies of the preserved objects accessed by users via the Access repository, it should enable the

restore and recovery of preserved objects in case of loss or corruption of the preserved objects in the Access Repository.

3.3 Access Repository

The Access Repository holds the digital assets made available to end users, and thus requires read-access from outside the repository organization. Publishers and archival processors will have write access to this repository in order to upload the objects to be preserved, i.e., snapshots/archived ROs. Once the research objects are uploaded, further changes should be disallowed. However, users should be allowed read-only access to these objects, unless they are marked as private by the publisher/archival processors. Moreover, this repository may enable read-write access to user-generated annotations that talk about the preserved objects (comments/ratings/etc.). The access copy of a research object should be the same as the secure copy in the Preservation Repository, but they do not necessarily need to be stored in the same way, i.e., they may be compressed in the Preservation Repository. Hence, it should be possible to reconstitute the access copies from the preservation copies. Additionally, the Access Repository may also hold additional content, such as the user-generated annotations mentioned above. Finally, this repository should implement a well defined API that enables the access to the research objects as a whole, potentially in different representations (e.g., as a ZIP archive, HTML page, metadata, linked data), or to the individual resources it aggregates (e.g., workflows, datasets), including all the semantic information associated.

4. Archival Processing of Research Objects

Figure 7. The RO Archival Processing Workflow.

Figure 7 offers a generalized RO archival processing workflow, based on the OAIS model, to receive submissions (SIP), archive (AIP), and make accessible (DIP) Research Objects from archival repositories. Specific details of how the above steps will be implemented will be largely affected by the technical architecture the repository employs and the formats that archives ingest and/or choose to use as the basis for preservation and/or access.

The specification for the RO model does not mandate any particular form for the representation of Research Objects. For instance, they could be accessed and maintained on the web through a RESTful web service exposing RDF/XML and Turtle¹³ representations. Practical use of the RO model has however shown that it is also beneficial to represent a research object as a single ZIP archive or as file system folders for the purposes of downloading, editing and archiving a research object.

¹³ David Beckett; Tim Berners-Lee. Turtle: Terse RDF Triple Language. January 2008. W3C Team Submission. <http://www.w3.org/TeamSubmission/turtle/>

A Research Object Bundle specification¹⁴ provides a way to collect the resources that are aggregated in a research object, represented as files in a ZIP archive, in addition to their metadata and annotations. The ZIP archive¹⁵ thus becomes a single representation of a research object which can be exported, archived, published and transferred like a regular file or resource.

Repositories could develop a Data or Dataset Type Preservation Plan (inspired by earlier media type preservation plans)¹⁶, as illustrated in the following example table (Table 1), and then develop specific archival processing transformation details for each of the file formats:

RO components	Data File Formats	Preservation Format(s)	Access Format(s)	Transformation Tool
Documents/Literature (e.g. papers that inspire the development of the RO)	.pdf, .txt, .html, .odfpdf, .txt, .html, .odfpdf, .txt, .html, .odf ...	
Experiment sketch	.pngpngpng ...	
Hypothesis	.txttxttxt ...	
Workflows	t2.flow, .wfbundle	.wfbundle	t2.flow, .wfbundle	
Workflow description	t2.flow, .wfbundle	.rdf (wf description graph)	.rdf (wf description graph)	Wf-RO Transformation Service (through scuf12-wfdesc)
Workflow input data (data set)	.txt, .csv, .xls ...	—	—	
Web services	URL	—	—	
Scripts	.py .javapy .javapy .java ...	
Workflow run (provenance)	.rdfrdf	.rdf	

¹⁴ This specification defines a file format for storage and distribution of Research Objects as a ZIP archive; called a Research Object Bundle (RO Bundle). RO Bundles allow capturing a Research Object to a single file or byte-stream by including its manifest, annotations and some or all of its aggregated resources for the purposes of exporting, archiving, publishing and transferring research objects. URL: <http://wf4ever.github.io/ro/bundle/2013-05-21/>

¹⁵ A Research Object Bundle is a structured [ZIP archive](#), specializing the [Adobe Universal Container Format](#) (UCF). UCF defines rules for how to represent an abstract collection of files (the abstract container) into a physical representation within a Zip archive (the physical container). The rules for Zip containers build upon and are backward compatible with the Zip technology used by Open Document Format (ODF).

¹⁶ Example of a Media type preservation plan is the Archivematica's wiki. https://www.archivematica.org/wiki/Media_type_preservation_plans

Workflow output data (data set: result maps, result graphs, etc.)	.txttxttxt ...	
Conclusions	.txttxttxt ...	
Manifest file (if present, must contain the [ORE] manifest for the research object)	.json	.rdf	---	
Annotations	.rdf, .txtrdf, .txtrdf, .txt ...	
Research Object as a whole	ZIP file, an RDF file, (i.e. its manifest)	ZIP file ...	ZIP archive, HTML page, metadata, linked data...	

Table 1. Data Type Preservation Plan (example)

4.1 Receive Submission Information Package (SIP)

The Receive SIP Process encompasses the means and/or mechanism for an RO content producer to submit an RO to the archives for preservation.

There are a series of steps that, at a minimum, should be completed.

Create an RO

In this creation phase, the contributor/producer prepares files for the RO to be created.

In the context of a scientific experiment we consider the preservation of at least the following scientific assets and their metadata:

- The hypothesis (or research question, depending on the type of experiment)
- A workflow-like sketch of the overall experiment
- One or more workflows
- Input data (e.g.: a list of example single-nucleotide polymorphisms, SNPs)
- Workflow runs (provenance data): data generated by a workflow system as a workflow is running.
- The results: they could be compiled from the different workflow outputs to one results file.
- The conclusions

It is very important to provide sufficient annotation of the inputs, outputs and the functions/purpose of each part of the workflow to ensure a clear interpretation and ensure that scientists know how to replay the workflows using the same input data, or re-run them with their own data.

An annotation provides additional metadata or descriptions that are somewhat about or related to the research object or some of its aggregated resources¹⁷.

Annotations may be provided primarily for human consumption (e.g. a description of a hypothesis that is tested by a workflow-based experiment), or for machine consumption (e.g. a structured description of the provenance of results generated by a workflow run). Both kinds of annotations are accommodated using the recommended Annotation Ontology structures¹⁸: i) `ao:Annotation`, which acts as a handle for the annotation, ii) `ao:annotatesResource`, which represents the resource(s)/RO(s) subjects to annotation, iii) `ao:body`, which points to an `rdfg:Graph` which contains the actual annotation.

Any aggregated resource of a research object can be annotated using the other Wf4Ever ontologies, standard ontologies like Dublin Core Terms, and third-party ontologies that may be domain-specific.

In practice, each annotation context is done as a separate RDF Graph (either a named graph or a separate resource). An `ro:AggregatedAnnotation` is then created, which specifies this graph as its `ao:body`, links to any aggregated resources using `ro:annotatesAggregatedResource`, and is itself aggregated by the `ro:ResearchObject` and contained within the `ro:Manifest`.

Implementation-wise, in the `ro:Manifest` one should only make assertions about the RO aggregation and minimal metadata such as when it was created, while all other assertions, such as typing an `ro:Resource` to be a `wfdesc:Workflow` or providing a `dc:description` is performed in annotations.

`dct:created` and `dc:creator` on the `ro:AggregatedAnnotation` will specify who made that assertion and added it to the research object.

If the annotation body has been created independently of the research object, for instance annotations of services made within the definition of a Taverna¹⁹ workflow, then `dc:creator` and `dct:created` can be specified also for the resource given by `ao:body`.

An example of general annotations applicable to the description of an RO is shown in Table 2.

Scientific domain	<code>dct:subject</code>
Description	<code>dct:description</code>
Institution	<code>dct:publisher</code>
Country	<code>pav:createdAt</code>
Author	<code>dct:creator</code>
Contributor	<code>dct:contributor</code>

¹⁷ An annotation is specified as an object [<http://wf4ever.github.io/ro/bundle/2013-05-21/#bib-UCF>]

¹⁸ Examples of expressing annotations to an RO and its components can be found in <http://wf4ever.github.io/ro-primer/> (sections 3.3 and 3.4)

¹⁹ An open source domain independent Workflow Management System: <http://www.taverna.org.uk/>

RO snapshot creator	roevo:wasSnapshotedBy
RO release/archive creator	roevo:wasArchivedBy
Notes	rdfs:comment
Keywords	roterms:keywords
Title	dct:title
Creation date	dct:created
Modification date	dct:modified
Purpose	roterms:performsTask
Dependencies (e.g., execution environment)	dct:requires Subproperties roterms:requiresHardware roterms:requiresSoftware roterms:requiresDataset
License	dct:license
Citations	dct:isReferencedBy
Technical contact	roterms:technicalContact
General documentation	cito:isDocumentedBy

Table 2. General annotations applicable to ROs (example)

Scientists will appreciate guidelines and Best Practices for producing high quality ROs. In this regard, we recommend following the **10 Best Practices for creating workflows**²⁰ defined in [8]. We envision that such instructions may differ between research communities, and publishers who wish to adopt RO technology may provide for digital submissions their own 'Instructions to Authors' for ROs. This could be implemented by different mappings of the MINIM model [9], which is explained later.

Finally, the RO of the experiment will be the container for the items that will be aggregated with the aid of the RO-enabled infrastructure. In terms of RDF and the RO model, we are instantiating a *ro:ResearchObject*, a sub-class of *ore:Aggregation*. The producer should fill in a title and description of the RO at the point of creation. She should receive a confirmation that the RO has been created and has been assigned a unique resolvable identifier (URI) in the Live Repository. She should also receive notifications when a new resource is added to that RO pack.

²⁰ These Best Practices were developed to encourage re-use and prevent workflow decay. They briefly consists of the following steps: 1) Make a sketch workflow; 2) Use modules; 3) Think about the output; 4) Provide input and output examples; 5) Annotate; 6) Make it executable from outside the local environment; 7) Choose services carefully; 8) Reuse existing workflows; 9) Test and validate; 10) Advertise and Maintain.

Add workflow, hypothesis, datasets, wf-runs, etc.

Aggregate resources, including provenance information and other related metadata. Each of the subsequent items in the RO is aggregated as a *ro:Resource*, a sub-class of *ore:AggregatedResource*.

The aggregation functionality should also enable receiving existing aggregations of scientific data and transforming them into RO compliant resources.

In order to specify the type of resource (hypothesis, conclusion, etc.), it could be used an ontology as the **roterms ontology** used in Wf4Ever²¹.

Each file is uploaded to the RO selecting the appropriate type. Then, an annotation should be added to the RO to specify that the file is of that type.

In case of adding workflows, a workflow pack may contain:

- 1) The workflow (e.g. t2.flow file)
- 2) A workflow diagram (flow chart)
- 3) Documentation of the workflow (name, date and version, authors -the main workflow constructor- and contributors -designers, web service developers, testers-, keywords, higher-level scientific description of workflow, technical specifications –execution environment and installation requirements platforms supported, description of the operations, functions and interactions in the workflow, web service documentation and specification, support desk-, references –possible case studies-, etc.)
- 4) Example data: sample input data (input file) and sample output data (result maps, result graphs, other), input file format instructions, execution time for example data set.

An Astronomy RO Example is available at: <http://wf4ever.github.com/ro/#astro-example-sec>

Because an RO is available as RDF, SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language can be used to sample its content.

Create/Verify metadata

It is recommended verifying that the RO created meets a minimum metadata as a whole (e.g.: Source; Contributor; Title; Description; Type; Subject; Creator; Date). Each of the RO's components should also meet a minimum metadata.

The Research Object metadata will be stored in a triple store, which is the primary source of information about them and can be queried using the SPARQL language.

The RO infrastructure also should generate metadata about ROs and their resources every time the RO is updated. These basic metadata may be:

- The author of the changes

²¹ <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/wf4ever/ro/wfannotations/roterms.owl#>

- The date
- Evolution information
- Automatic relations between resources

Identify/Approve folder structure

Verify that the SIP conforms to the folder structure required for processing in the Live Repository.

As it was commented previously, practical use of the RO model has shown that it is beneficial to represent a research object as a single ZIP archive or as file system folders for the purposes of downloading, editing and archiving a research object. For instance:

- | | |
|----------------|--------------|
| - biblio | - datasets |
| - produced | - inputs |
| - used | - results |
| - config | - workflows |
| - scripts | - components |
| - setup | - main |
| - software | - nested |
| - web services | |

It is recommended to populate automatically the folder structure to the extent that it is possible and include annotations that enable this automatic population (workflow, dataset, configuration, bibliography). File format can be used or at least help in the automatic population of folders, for example when no resource type is given by the user.

Example of annotation mapping relationships and other information exposed in the tree-folder structure:

A document is a produced publication in bibliography

A document is a referenced/used publication in bibliography

All files in /config/files are configuration files

All small files in /config/soft represent needed software dependencies

All small files in /config/ws represent web services used

All files in subfolders of /data/all/user_input/ are user-provided required files

All files in /data/all/user_input/wfname are user-provided required files for workflow wfname

All files in of /data/all/user_input/common are user-provided required files shared by several workflows

All files in subfolders of /data/all/outcome/ are files produced in workflows

All files in subfolders of /data/all/outcome/wfname are files produced by workflow wfname

All files in subfolders of /data/all/results are actual final results of the RO

All files in /data/subset are sample data used to check reproducibility and repeatability of workflows

All files in /process/bin/ are binary files imported in Taverna workflows

All files in /process/scripts/ are scripts inserted into Taverna workflows

All t2flow files inside /workflows/main are the actual workflows used in the RO

All t2flow files inside /workflows/nested are small workflows inserted into one or several main workflows

All files and symlinks inside /workflows/main/wfname are related to workflow wfname

All files in subfolders of /workflows/main/*/income/ files are input files

All files in subfolders of /workflows/main/*/income/wfname2 are output files of workflow wfname1

All files in subfolders of /workflows/main/*/prov_runs are provenance executions of a workflow

Some of the products are plots, other are tabular data, other binary FITS 2D images

Annotations accounting for information not exposed in the tree-folder structure:

Author of an annotation

Author and co-authors of a workflow; reference link to a re-used workflow and its author

Who has performed the execution of a workflow leading to the results provided in the RO

Computing execution environment of the RO and local software dependencies

Special access requirements to web services

Datasets provider: person, webpage, survey, data release, etc.

How much time does it take to run a workflow using the full data and the provided subsample

The number of elements of the sample dataset where one workflow and/or RO iterates

Previous and subsequent workflows to be executed, as described in the experimental protocol

Research institution, country, and scientific domain of the RO

The actual size of the RO and/or a folder

The version of a workflow

Run checklist for completeness (optional)

We recommend providing users with a mechanism of quality insurance, as our so-called checklist evaluation tool [9, 10]. Its basic function is to assess that all required information and descriptions about the aggregated resources are present and complete. Additionally, according to explicit requirements defined in a checklist, the tool can also assess the accessibility of those resources aggregated in an RO, in order to increase the trust on the understanding of the RO.

Wf4Ever's checklist tool is built upon the Minim checklist ontology [10], defined using Ontology Web Language, which provides the structure for specifying quality requirements in a checklist using RDF.

The Minim model has four key components, as illustrated by Figure 8:

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- A **Constraint**, which associates a model (checklist) to use with an RO, for a specific assessment purpose, e.g. reviewing an RO containing sufficient information before being shared.
- A **Model**, which enumerates the set of requirements to be considered, which may be declared at levels of MUST, SHOULD or MAY be satisfied for the model as a whole.
- A **Requirement**, which is the key part for expressing the concrete quality requirements of an RO, for example, the presence of certain information about an experiment, or liveness (accessibility) of a data server.
- A **Rule**, which can be a *SoftwareRequirementRule*, to specify the software to be present in the operating environment; a *ContentMatchRequirementRule*, to specify the presence of certain pattern in the assessed data; or a *DataRequirementRule*, for specifying data resource to be aggregated in an RO.

Figure 8. An overview of the Minim model.

Checklist evaluation should be a read-only function, so there is no obvious risk of unintended data modification.

Checklist evaluation results may expose information about the content of a Research Object (Figure 9). As a general rule, the results of a checklist evaluation should be provided only to agents who themselves have permission to access the RO contents.

Interpreting GWAS results with pathways and text mining

This pack contains workflows for interpreting SNP associations from a GWAS on human metabolite variation, using pathways from the KEGG metabolic pathway database and Gene Ontology biological process associations from text mining.

✓ **Target [Pack405](#) fully satisfies checklist for ready-to-release.**

- ✓ Experiment hypothesis is present
- ✓ Workflow design sketch is present
- ✓ All workflow definitions are accessible
- ✓ All web services used by workflows are accessible
- ✓ Input data is present
- ✓ Experiment conclusions are present

[Wf4Ever project](#)

Figure 9. Example of checklist evaluation results applying the Minim model.

Submit SIP

The final step will be the actual transfer of the files from the contributor to the Live Repository. Digital objects in the Live Repository are stored using the Research Object Model.

Administrative metadata that should be recorded as part of the ingest process includes:

- Contributor contact information who submitted the file (e.g. Name, Agency/Institution, email)
- Description of data files being ingested
- Date files ingested
- Number of (data) files ingested
- Names of the (data) files ingested
- Size of the collection of files ingested
- Validity value for the data files
- Format
- Access restrictions (default: public record, no restrictions)
- Submission Agreement identification (if one is established)

Receive acknowledgement of submitted files

With the completion of the ingest quality assurance tasks, the contributor should receive an acknowledgement whether the submitted data passed or failed the Quality Assurance process, and if failed, suggestions regarding what needs to be corrected to provide an acceptable submission.

Each RO may have a label/Tag, identifying a more detailed information of its state, e.g., 'internally-reviewed', 'in progress of internal revision', 'in progress of modifications', 'peer-reviewed', 'ready-to-publish', etc. There should be a service or a functionality entity, following the RO evolution model [11], defining the formats and links used to change the lifecycle stage of a research object, most importantly to create an immutable snapshot or archive from a mutable live research object, as well as to retrieve the evolution provenance of a research object (the evolution metadata that are generated for each state transition).

When an RO is in an immutable stage (snapshot or archived), the contributor should also receive an acknowledgement from the archival organization whether the RO she submitted was acceptable and is moving forward to preservation, or was rejected, along with the reason for rejection.

Key questions for the Repository with regard to the Submission process:

- ✓ How is the mechanism to be used by content Producers to create an RO and aggregate resources to it?
- ✓ How the ROs' components have to be prepared and packed to be ingested?
- ✓ How should RO components be named for transfer to the Repository?
- ✓ How should RO component files be organized for transfer to the Repository?
- ✓ What RO metadata Producers are required to include?
- ✓ How will RO be validated for transfer?

4.2 Quality Assurance

This function validates the successful transfer of the SIP to the Live Repository.

The archival processor should perform an evaluation of different quality dimensions of an RO, such as its completeness (all information needed by the RO is present), executability (all resources and dependencies needed to run the RO are present) and repeatability (all resources and metadata to repeat an experiment are present).

Run virus check

Firstly, to ensure that the files are clean and free from viruses, complete a virus check on the submitted files. In less sophisticated content submission approaches, the archival processor may need to manually run a virus checking utility on the files received. In more sophisticated ingestion applications, the ingest program may be able to run the virus checker program on behalf of the contributor, and notify the contributor and

archival processor when a file has been found to be infected, and require the contributor to resubmit a new version of the file found to be infected.

When infected files are identified, they will need to be logged and the contributor notified for some sort of remediation. In the case of the sophisticated ingest process, the contributor may receive a success / failure message directly from the ingest application, and be immediately informed of a file rejected due to virus infection, and be prompted to resubmit. In Repositories with more manually-oriented processes, the archival processor will need to notify the contributor of the acceptance or rejection of the submitted files.

Check the format and link relations

The repository should check the format and link relations before creating or updating the AIP. As part of the initial validation process, the archival processor may choose to employ file format checking / metadata extraction utilities, such as FITS²² (File Information Toolset) (which wraps several tools).

Verify that all files have been received, optimally against the manifest that was created when the files were packaged; verify that there are no extra files added to the package, and that the files have arrived intact and unaltered through the transfer process.

Research Objects will generally contain workflows. One workflow format submitted may generate an RO using a service like a transformation service. This RO will include the original workflow, plus a workflow bundle (a new workflow format), metadata extracted from the workflow regarding its structure (e.g., inputs, outputs), and other metadata generated. The resulting RDF document is aggregated in the RO and used as the annotation body of the workflow, thus creating a link between the aggregated workflow file and the workflow description in RDF.

In order to assess if a workflow is functional, it is useful to be able to (re)-execute a workflow. Therefore, the Repository should have a service/function for features such as "Run this workflow please" and "Show me the data from that workflow run".

The ROs exposed by this service each represent a particular workflow run, structured to show inputs, outputs, console logs, provenance and annotations containing wfprov and wfdesc mappings.

Navigating the workflow runs should allow inspection of workflow status, outputs and other resources exposed by the underlying workflow server. A client may also create a new run by uploading a workflow definition, provide inputs and initiate running the workflow.

Run checklist for completeness

There should be a service/function for testing completeness, executability, repeatability and other desired quality features of a Research Object.

In order to perform a checklist evaluation, the following data should be required:

²² The File Information Tool Set (FITS) identifies, validates, and extracts technical metadata for various file formats. It wraps several third-party open source tools, normalizes and consolidates their output, and reports any errors.

- A publicly accessible Research Object which will be evaluated.
- A publicly accessible minimum information model resource (as MINIM model) from which the checklist definition is obtained²³.
- A selected checklist definition from the model, for example to test “repeatability”.
- A target resource with respect to which the evaluation is performed; the default target is the RO itself, but a component within the RO may be selected.

Validate naming conventions and folder structure

The Wf4Ever team recommends that archival organizations discuss and come to agreement on a general organizational structure for the ROs to facilitate data access by using it as the basis for a browse/navigation organizational structure for end users. Submitted ROs should conform to these guidelines.

The Wf4Ever team also recommends filing naming conventions for the ROs and their resources (data sources/workflow names/ID names, etc.). The Repository will need to define as part of its submission policies the actions it will take when received ROs do not conform to the naming and/or organizational guidelines.

Validate RO metadata is completed to Archive’s specifications

From a long-term preservation perspective, the RO metadata is one of the most valuable components. It would be convenient to identify a subset of required metadata elements that serve as a common guideline for all RO infrastructure developers (descriptive, technical and administrative metadata).

Lack of technical metadata can negatively impact the long-term accessibility and management of the ROs. It is also an important aspect for future migration planning.

Send acknowledgement to RO contributor

At the completion of the Quality Assurance checks an acknowledgement should be sent to the RO contributor notifying her whether the submitted data passed or failed the Quality Assurance process, and if failed, suggestions regarding what needs to be corrected to provide an acceptable submission.

The Quality Assurance process could be assisted in by the use of a workflow system that provides the task list, and allows the archival processor to record the pass/fail status of each step in the Quality Assurance process (Appendix A). The workflow could then be programmed to send an automated response to the contributor at the completion of the workflow. The workflow log could also serve as documentary evidence of the Quality Assurance steps the archival processor completed when the RO was submitted, as well as the final status of the Quality Assurance check. Alternatively, a simple electronic document version of the checklist could be produced, and saved as an administrative document in the AIP.

²³ An example of a simple minim model can be found at <https://github.com/wf4ever/ro-catalogue/blob/master/v0.1/simple-requirements/simple-requirements-minim.rdf>

Further, the contributor should receive an acknowledgment/notification when an RO is in an immutable stage and is moving forward to preservation.

Key questions for the Repository with regard to the Quality Assurance process:

- ✓ How to handle received ROs that are not named according to Repository submission guidelines?
- ✓ How to handle received ROs that are not organized based on Repository submission guidelines?
- ✓ What quality features of an RO must be validate / evaluate?
- ✓ How will archives validate / evaluate the completeness of the RO metadata?
- ✓ How will the Repository deal with missing metadata?
- ✓ What security measures are taken to ensure the safety of the submission and the submitted data before their storage in the Preservation Repository?

4.3 Generate Archival Information Package (AIP)

This function will transform one or more SIPs into one or more AIPs, for long term storage, and deposit them into the Preservation Repository.

On the one hand, the Preservation Repository should provide capacities concerned mainly with the static aspects of preservation, e.g., adding resources to permanent storage, managing internal data models, maintaining the RO resources associated semantic metadata, indexing, searching and protection of resources, basic versioning mechanisms, etc. Ideally, the Preservation Repository will also include services to perform periodic integrity checks, and automatically restore or recover preserved objects in the event a corrupted state.

On the other hand, and it was commented before, there should be a service or a functionality entity defining the formats and links used to change the lifecycle stage of a research object, most importantly to create an immutable snapshot or archive from a mutable live research object, as well as to retrieve the evolution provenance of a research object (the evolution metadata that are generated for each state transition).

This service/function will provide capabilities to the preservation infrastructure with respect to the dynamic aspects of preservation of ROs. It should prescribe services for the execution of RO resources, such as workflows, the management of RO evolution, including versioning²⁴ and curation activities, and the provision of monitoring and notification mechanisms to ensure the correct preservation of ROs.

²⁴ We consider an RO version as a specific form or variant of an RO that is normally created after applying changes to an existing variant. A version has an associated state, e.g., live, archived, and they are related to each other via direct relationships (e.g., wasRevisionOf) or via contribution dependencies (e.g., derivedFrom, relatesTo).

Monitoring and notification activities

The Preservation Repository should make sure that Research Objects can be used and run in long time by regularly checking their status with a set of internal and external services. These should include the checklist evaluation function that checks the data description and dependencies on external resources.

One of the most important aspects to be monitored is the stability of the resources (Figure 10). The stability measurement is based on the evaluation of the RO along time. The idea is to capture concrete values provided by the evaluation of the RO in different moments of its evolution or, in other words, by subjecting the snapshots of an RO to the checklist evaluation (that may vary its purpose). It will test the ability of a Research Object to achieve its original purpose after being subject of changes on its resources.

Figure 10. Monitoring scheme of the stability of the resources.

Specialist algorithms must evaluate each of the actions captured in the provenance trail of an RO. This evaluation can give an overview of the RO quality throughout time.

The checklist monitoring service is going to base on data provided by stability service. The stability service stores the checklist history. It means that if the RO quality changed, the fresh checklist evaluation result needs to be stored in the history. The stability service provides earlier stored data in an Atom (RSS) format via defined API.

Finally, it is also recommended providing notifications to the user about the reliability, stability and completeness together with the set of rules of the checklist service every time that the completeness of the Research Object changes. To this end, the checklist service/function should be run against all the Research Objects periodically in order to detect changes and store them. In that way, the Repository is able to create a trace of reliability over time and keep the users informed.

Therefore, notifications should be generated when RO quality goes below a defined threshold (determined using checklist service), when the integrity check fails or when obsolete workflow formats are detected.

Create a safe copy of RO metadata file

It is recommended to create a safe copy of the metadata file (manifest.rdf), which is embedded within the RO. It represents the state of the RO at the time it was submitted to the Repository, and it should include the minimum metadata defined by the archival organization. According to the OAIS model, this information would be stored and managed in the Data Management module.

Replace and format transformation (if necessary)

The Preservation Repository should give the possibility to define migration plans that allow performing a batch update of resources from one format to another, when necessary. In case of workflows, this may be applied for instance when a flat Taverna t2flow format should be converted to a complex scuf2 format (which, nota bene, uses the RO model similarly to research objects). Other case could be a batch update of workflows that depend on a malfunctioning external resource.

This is where it will be helpful to have a Preservation Data Type Plan, to streamline the decision to reformat, as well as identify the target format to reformat a resource to, and what tools and/or processes to execute to transform the resource (e.g. a workflow-RO transformation service/function).

If the Repository chooses to reformat a resource, it should retain the original, as it is unknown if future transformations will be necessary, and if those subsequent transformations will be most effective sourced from the original format or the reformatted version. Over the course of an RO's life, as the software technology continues to evolve, the object may require several reformattings. The reformatting process should also be recorded in the archival metadata record, and even in the RO metadata file, to maintain the lineage and manipulations performed.

Establish fixity value/mechanism

The Preservation Repository should offer checksums checking (at file level). This function will provide a means to verify the bit-level integrity of files managed by this storage. The Repository needs to establish the processes and tools to:

- periodically re-compute the fixity values on the files and compare them with the baseline,
- establish a replication mechanism to make a security copy(ies) to be used when a damaged file needs to be restored,
- compute the fixity values on the replicas to make sure they are in sync with the "master",
- replace damaged files as they are identified.

RO working copies in the Access Repository will also be periodically verified with the secure copies to ensure their fixity.

Create Archival Metadata Record

In order to make the RO accessible and to be able to manage it for the long-term, an archival metadata record needs to be created. In the OAIS model, this information would be stored and managed in the Data Management module. This record will describe and manage the RO, which might be comprised of numerous files. Archival metadata goes beyond the basic descriptive information, and provides:

- a) Technical information about the RO being managed (software application name and version, technical characteristics, etc.);
- b) Administrative information (use rights, access constraints, provenance, ongoing record of any changes made to the RO after it's been ingested by the Repository (e.g. initial processing, or future format transformations or migrations), information about the contributor, and if applicable, the submission agreement, etc.)
- c) Descriptive information to facilitate access to the RO being managed, including title, author, date, keywords, etc.

As an RO is comprised of numerous files, the archival metadata record should, at a minimum, store the “manifest” that lists all of the files that comprise it, or a pointer to a manifest file. In addition, the Repository may also want to record in its archival database the basic descriptive (name, size, date created, date modified), and technical metadata (type of file or format, application name and version) for each of the files that comprise the RO.

The Repository may want to be selective with regard to which RO metadata fields are extracted into the archival metadata record. The descriptive fields that map to the Dublin Core metadata fields are a good start, and could then be expanded to any additional fields that aid in access.

In brief, we recommend that the template should comprise:

- Unique ID
- Fixity info
- Format
- Extract RO metadata
- Created descriptive metadata
- Created technical metadata
- Created administrative metadata

Create AIP and add record to Preservation Repository

In this phase, the RO representing the Archival Information Package can be “packaged” and deposited into the Preservation Repository. What constitutes the Archival “Record” will be defined by each Repository. However, at a minimum, it should include the original (and reformatted, if applicable) RO including the original collection of data files and the originally received RO metadata file.

The technical physical manifestation of the Archival Information Package will depend upon each Repository's technical implementation. This could entail adding data to a database and/or adding files to a file system designated for archival use. PREMIS²⁵ and METS²⁶ can be used to document the package specification. Packaging tools, such as zip, could also be used to create a package-type object that contains the file-related artifacts for the RO being preserved.

Create security copy of the AIP

Security copies of the AIP record should be created and retained. In the event that the AIP is corrupted or lost, it may be recovered from a security copy.

There are a variety of media and storage options available for storing the security copy. Optimally, the security copies should be stored in a geographically distributed location. Consideration must be made regarding how the ongoing integrity of the security copy(ies) will be monitored and maintained, especially for offline implementations.

Key questions for the Repository with regard to the Generate AIP process:

- ✓ What are the mappings between expected submitted formats and their companion Preservation Master formats? (refer to your Data Type Preservation Plan)
- ✓ What tools and processes will be employed to transform a RO component received in one format to another format to produce the Preservation Master?
- ✓ What tools, techniques, or strategies will the Repository employ to populate the missing technical fields?
- ✓ What method will the Repository use to compute, store, re-compute, and compare fixity values for both the Preservation Master and Preservation Master Security Copy(ies)?
- ✓ How would someone perform an audit check to view and/or validate that a file's integrity is intact?
- ✓ What metadata elements comprise the archival metadata record? / What metadata, (if any), are being created by the archive for inclusion in the AIP and DIP?
- ✓ Will the Repository use a special packaging mechanism (e.g. METS)?
- ✓ Who will have access to the Archival Information Packages? What type of access (read, write)?
- ✓ What will the mechanism(s) to create a security copy(ies), and on what type of media format(s) will the security copy(ies) be stored?
- ✓ What is the mechanism and frequency that the security copy(ies) will be validated?

²⁵ PREMIS - Preservation Metadata Maintenance Activity. <http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/>

²⁶ METS - Metadata Encoding & Transmission Standard. <http://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>

- ✓ What is the process for restoring the Preservation Master in the event that it is lost or corrupted?
- ✓ What is the process for restoring a Security Copy in the event that it is lost or corrupted?

4.4 Generate Dissemination Information Package (DIP)

Accepts a dissemination request, retrieves the AIP from the Preservation Repository, moves a copy of the data to the Access Repository for further processing, and notifies the Coordinate Access Activities that the DIP is ready for delivery.

Create the Access Copy

Preparing an access/working copy of the preserved ROs (to minimize access to the Preservation Master), plus the additional archival processing tasks related to the arrangement and description including creating access metadata, and incorporating the DIP into the Repository's access information organizational structure.

Working copies will be periodically verified with the secure copies in the Preservation Repository to ensure their fixity.

They will be placed in a system and repository that is accessible by end users.

Data will be transformed to a requested format on the fly. Binary data should be available in the format they were submitted. Finally, Research Objects should also be available as HTML pages.

Minimum access metadata recommended: URI; Creator; Date; Size; Number of annotations; Relations (was output from; etc.)

Create access aid derivatives

To facilitate end users' search and retrieval tasks, the archival processor may produce additional RO derivatives that may assist users in evaluating the relevance of the data to their search needs without having to download and access the entire RO. Some potential access derivatives:

- Create HTML version of the Repository's customized RO metadata file. In addition to the descriptive information, that can be a significant assistance to a researcher to determine if the RO is relevant to her search needs, the metadata file should also define the collection of data attributes that comprise the underlying RO. The RO metadata file is produced in RDF which is not a very convenient format for human comprehension, so a much more user-friendly view of the metadata file is needed. Publishing an HTML version of the RO metadata file in the Repository's access interface allows end users to preview and inspect the RO metadata prior to deciding to download it.
- Create a zip file containing all of the files in the RO. As the RO are commonly comprised of several files, the end user's download will be facilitated by providing them with the collection of files in a single package file.

Figure 11. Three views of the research object structure.

- A visualization of the evolution of a research object: any graph of research objects or similar resources that are related to the inspected research object in terms of evolution (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Research object evolution panel.

- A panel showing annotations related to the currently selected resource (Figure 13).

The panel, titled "Annotations for the selected resource", displays a table of annotations for a selected resource. Below the table are buttons for "Add annotation", "Delete selected annotations", "Add relation", and "Import annotation".

	Resource	Value	Action
<input type="checkbox"/>	[This item]	creator http://www.myexperiment.org/users/18931	Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	[This item]	description This screenshot shows the "Elevation plot..." workflow with the nested workflows compact.	Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	[This item]	source http://www.myexperiment.org/files/584	Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	[This item]	title Workflow compact	Edit

by Piotr Holubowicz , Chrissier , 30 May 2012 10:26

Figure 13. Resource annotation panel.

Verify Catalog and Digital Collection access

After the RO entries and/or datasets have been added to the access systems, they should be tested to verify that they are accessible. This can be as simple as navigating through the catalog interface, issuing some test searches, and verifying that the new items are returned in the search results lists. In the case that the research objects are being made available online, the dataset display interface and dataset download mechanisms should also be tested to verify that the research objects can be downloaded.

Update Archival Metadata Record

The archival metadata may be updated with metadata regarding the use of resources (information on user registration and possible annotations made by users respect to the resource) and the derivative resources produced during the DIP generation.

Key questions for the Repository with regard to the Generate DIP process:

- ✓ What format will be used for the Access Copy? Same format at Preservation Master? An alternate, compressed format?
- ✓ What tool(s) are necessary to create the Access/Use Copy?
- ✓ What access derivatives seem appropriate for your ROs?
- ✓ What tools do you need to produce these derivatives?
- ✓ How will ROs be arranged / organized within your archival collection? What constitutes a Collection?
- ✓ Will individual ROs be entered into your Repository Catalog? If not, how will users find out about the individual ROs? If yes, how will the ROs be entered into your Repository Catalog?
- ✓ What type of finding aid will you create to describe your RO datasets?
- ✓ What technology platform and software will be the basis for your RO digital collection?
- ✓ How will RO be added to the digital collection?
- ✓ What metadata is necessary to describe and/or manage the RO record in the digital collection?
- ✓ How will the RO be organized and arranged/categorized in your digital collection?
- ✓ How will users search and access ROs from your digital collection?
- ✓ How will the ROs be presented to your users through the digital collection interface?
- ✓ What test cases will you use to validate the access to your newly added RO?

5. Conclusions

Some of the special considerations regarding the archival processing of research objects include:

- ROs are usually comprised of several files that must all be preserved together.
- The need to support live, dynamically changing research objects as well as immutable snapshots that are intended for long-term preservation.
- Comprehensive metadata record. The total metadata model should be able to be designed in such a way that allows the Repository to support a variety of digital formats.
- Some of the ROs datasets will require significant storage space, especially when considering the multiple copies suggested for sustaining the long-term preservation of digital artifacts.
- The provision of services or functionalities for the execution of RO resources, such as workflows, and the management of RO evolution, including versioning and curation activities.
- Monitoring and notification of workflow decay or other issues compromising the reproducibility of the experiments.

As a result, research object-infrastructure design decisions should include these considerations in terms of functionality and policy:

- Modular system implementation (support flexible maintenance, extension, integration and interoperability).
- Native RO support. It should be implemented alongside the RO model.
- Implementation of well-defined and well-documented interfaces (suitable basis of interoperability).
- Well-defined migration plans to perform a batch update of resources from one format to another, if necessary.

Repositories can begin with a relatively low-tech and can evolve to more sophisticated technological solutions as resources (people, money, time and technology) are available. Regardless of the level of technical sophistication of the solution, however, Repositories will benefit from diagramming and describing their archival processing process, establishing a sound RO data organizational strategy (e.g., what constitutes a “collection”, a “series”, etc., and how the datasets should be organized for both preservation storage and end user access) and defining how the RO metadata file will be managed (e.g., how the metadata will be updated and filled in case of key missing fields).

Establishing a strong archival processing foundation will then facilitate the ongoing evolution and development of the total archival solution.

6. References²⁸

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²⁸ All URLs in the document have been revised on 05/06/2013.

7. APPENDIX A: Research Object Submission Checklist

Step #	Step Description	Pass / Fail	Comment
2.1	Run virus check		
2.2	Check the format and link relations		
2.3	Run checklist for completeness		
2.4	Validate naming conventions and folder structure		A Fail may just be an indicator that the archival processor will need to do some re-arrangement when preparing the AIP
2.5	Verify workflow runs		
2.6	Validate RO metadata		A Fail may just be an indicator that the archival processor will need to do some auto-populating when preparing the AIP.
2.7	Send acknowledgement to RO contributor		

8. APPENDIX B: Steps to create an Archival Information Package (AIP)

Step #	Step Description	Pass / Fail	Comment
3.1	Checklists/Monitoring activities		
3.2	Create a safe copy of RO metadata file		
3.3	Replace and format transformation (if necessary)		
3.4	Establish fixity value/mechanism		
3.5	Create Archival Metadata Record		
3.6	Create AIP and add record to Preservation Repository		
3.7	Create security copy of Preservation Master		

9. APPENDIX C: Steps to create a Dissemination Information Package (DIP)

Step #	Step Description	Pass / Fail	Comment
4.1	Create the Access copy		
4.2	Create access aid derivatives		
4.3	Create Catalog Entry and Finding Aids (optional)		
4.4	Add to Digital Collection		
4.5	Verify Catalog and Digital Collection access		
4.6	Update Archival Metadata Record		